

Filename: Nugen-RNA library 13_24.HSD5000

Gel Images

Samples
patient_site_day-of-sampling

- 13 : 2_ETA_3
- 14 : 2_ETA_6
- 15 : 2_BAL_9
- 16 : 5_ETA_3
- 17 : 5_ETA_9
- 18 : 5_ETA_15
- 19 : 8_ETA_4
- 20 : 8_ETA_9
- 21 : 8_ETA_12
- 22 : 1_ETA_6
- 23 : 1_ETA_9
- 24 : 1_BAL_VAP

Default image (Contrast 50%), Image is Scaled to Sample, Image is Scaled to view larger Molecular Weight range

Sample Info

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A1	2250	Ladder		Issue with ladder peak detection (too many peaks detected); Ladder
B1	4720			
C1	13900			
D1	13400			
E1	13800			
F1	12600			
G1	12000			
H1	19000			
A2	10700			
B2	6680			
C2	5030			
D2	5000			
E2	9150			
F2	16300			
G2	4250			

A1: Ladder

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A1	2250	Ladder		Issue with ladder peak detection (too many peaks detected); Ladder

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	400	-	41100	-		Lower Marker
100	237	-	3640	10.54		
250	264	-	1620	11.74		
400	262	-	1010	11.67		
600	264	-	677	11.76		
790	23.0	-	44.9	1.03		
1000	279	-	429	12.42		
1500	240	-	246	10.68		
2500	257	-	158	11.45		
3500	245	-	108	10.91		
5000	175	-	53.8	7.79		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

B1

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B1	4720			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	268	-	27500	-		Lower Marker
281	4400	-	24100	93.31		
888	316	-	546	6.69		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

C1

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C1	13900			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	209	-	21400	-		Lower Marker
286	13900	-	74600	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

D1

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D1	13400			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	209	-	21400	-		Lower Marker
260	13400	-	79100	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

E1

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
E1	13800			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	221	-	22700	-		Lower Marker
251	13800	-	84600	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

F1

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
F1	12600			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	239	-	24500	-		Lower Marker
259	12600	-	74800	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

G1

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
G1	12000			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	243	-	24900	-		Lower Marker
257	12000	-	71500	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

H1

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
H1	19000			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	205	-	21000	-		Lower Marker
265	19000	-	110000	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

A2

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A2	10700			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	246	-	25200	-		Lower Marker
257	10700	-	64200	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

B2

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B2	6680			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	274	-	28100	-		Lower Marker
281	6680	-	36600	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

C2

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C2	5030			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	265	-	27100	-		Lower Marker
250	5030	-	30900	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

D2

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D2	5000			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	320	-	32800	-		Lower Marker
239	5000	-	32300	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

E2

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
E2	9150			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	301	-	30900	-		Lower Marker
251	9150	-	56100	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

F2

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
F2	16300			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	184	-	18900	-		Lower Marker
270	16300	-	93000	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

G2

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
G2	4250			

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	310	-	31800	-		Lower Marker
260	3080	-	18200	72.46		
654	1170	-	2750	27.54		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

Profile Comparison

Samples

File	Indicator	Well ID	Comment
File 1	■ —	C2	
File 1	■ —	G2	

Files used in the Profile Comparison

File	Comments	Filename
File 1		O:\Laboratoire_Bacterio_Virologie\VIROLOGIE\Severine\Julien Microbiome Damien Roux\arn trio 2 purifie 2018-02-26 - 16.26.41.HSD5000